

Brown planthopper populations on resistant varieties treated with a resurgence-causing insecticide

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Previous laboratory and field experiments at IRRI have shown that the application of certain insecticides to susceptible rice varieties can induce resurgence of brown planthopper (BPH) populations. Because most Philippine farmers grow BPH-resistant varieties, we sought to determine if high BPH populations would develop on resistant varieties sprayed with a resurgence-causing insecticide. The varieties tested were IR20 (no gene for resistance); IR26 and IR29 (*Bph 1* gene); and IR32, IR36, IR40, and IR42 (*bph 2* gene). The entries were sprayed 7 times with cypermethrin in 300 liters water at 20 g a.i./ha. The BPH population was assessed twice a week by counting the BPH in 10 randomly selected hills/replication.

Biotypes 1 and 2 were predominant. The highest populations were on IR20 (susceptible to all biotypes), on IR29 and IR26 (susceptible to biotype 2) (see figure). All varieties with the *bph 2* gene, except IR40, had low populations. In previous field tests IR40 was less resistant to biotype 2 than IR32, IR36, and IR42. The study indicates that BPH populations remain low on varieties that are highly resistant to the prevailing biotype in spite of being sprayed with a resurgence-causing insecticide.

Brown planthopper populations on susceptible (IR20) and resistant varieties sprayed with a resurgence-inducing insecticide. IRRI, 1979.

Resurgence can be a serious problem for farmers when a biotype shifts and a previously resistant variety is rendered susceptible (this happened with IR26 in Indonesia and the Philippines). Although

this is speculation, we are concerned about the possibility that application of resurgence-causing insecticides could accelerate biotype selection on resistant varieties. ■

Soluble silicic acid and insoluble silica contents in leaf sheaths of rice varieties carrying different BPH-resistance genes

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In experiments to identify the chemical factors that influence varietal resistance to the brown planthopper (BPH), we found that soluble silicic acid, common in rice plants, strongly inhibits sucking by the BPH. Such inhibitory action was

effective at rates as low as 0.01 mg Si/ml. To test the assumption that soluble silicic acid might be involved in BPH resistance, we compared soluble and insoluble silica contents in the rice leaf sheaths of 28 varieties. Soluble silicic acid was extracted with 70% ethanol and measured colorimetrically by the molybdc acid method. Leaf sheaths after ethanol extraction were digested with a mixture of nitric acid, sulfuric acid, and 60% perchloric acid (5:1:2, vol/vol) for the analysis of insoluble silica. The residues were ashed in the

digested samples and the silica contents were weighed.

The absence of significant differences in contents of soluble silicic acid and insoluble silica among susceptible and resistant varieties (see table) indicates that silicic compounds do not influence BPH resistance. That was supported by evidence that the resistance level of Mudgo grown in a silica-free culture solution did not change. The silicic acid, usually distributed in the peripheral tissues outside the BPH phloem-sucking area, possibly influences phloem